

COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS AND 40-YEAR CHANGES IN THE ONSET OF VARIOUS FORMS OF SCHIZOPHRENIA IN THE FERGANA VALLEY POPULATION

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Abstract. *The article presents a comparative analysis of the onset of various forms of schizophrenia in the Fergana Valley population over a 40-year period (1984-2024). The aim of the study was to assess changes in the clinical manifestations of disease onset, focusing on acute and gradual forms of onset. A retrospective analysis was conducted using statistical methods: calculation of relative risk (RR), confidence intervals (95% CI), chi-square, and p-values. A statistically significant increase in cases with gradual onset manifestations and a decrease in the proportion of onsets with reduced energy potential have been established. The identified trends may reflect both improvements in diagnostic approaches and changes in biopsychosocial factors influencing disease manifestation. The obtained results contribute to a deeper understanding of clinical and epidemiological changes in the structure of schizophrenia and can be used to optimize early diagnosis and prevention.*

Keywords: *schizophrenia, onset, acute onset, Fergana Valley.*

Introduction

Schizophrenia is one of the most severe and socially significant mental disorders, characterized by a chronic course, a variety of clinical forms, and a substantial impact on personality functioning. The relevance of the study focused on the onset of various forms of schizophrenia, especially from a long-term retrospective perspective, is due to the need to improve diagnostic approaches, predict the course of the illness, and develop individualized intervention strategies.

Over the past decades, significant changes have been observed both in the structure of the disease itself and in its primary manifestations. Analysis of the 40-year dynamics of schizophrenia onset in the Fergana Valley population holds special scientific and practical value, as it allows for the examination of social, environmental, and biological factors' influence on the initial forms of the disease.

The aim of this study is to comparatively assess the clinical forms of schizophrenia onset in 1984 and 2024, identify stable and variable trends, and determine the significance of statistical shifts in the structure of the disease's initial manifestations.

The study analyzed the comparative characteristics of schizophrenia onset with various courses and the 40-year changes in the Fergana Valley population.

The presented numerical data indicate that the onset of schizophrenia with various courses is confirmed by the following detection frequencies of 7 different clinical manifestations, registered according to changes from 1984 to 2024: acute onset - from 33.4% to 32.5% (decrease of 0.9%), onset with primary disorders - from 66.6% to 67.5% (increase of 0.9%), of which onset with asthenic-neurosis-like disorders - from 18.8% to 18.2% (decrease of 0.6%), onset with negative disorders - from 12.8% to 15.4% (increase of 2.6%), onset with psychopathic-like disorders - from 8.9% to 11.4% (increase of 2.5%), onset with thymopathic disorders - from 8.9% to 11.5% (increase of 2.6%), onset with reduction of psychoenergetic potential - from 17.2% to 11.1% (decrease of 3.1%).

Overall, a comparative analysis of the onset of schizophrenia with various courses shows the following: the total number of patients with an acute onset of the disease is 357 people (32.8%), of which 146 (33.4%) were as of 1984 and 211 (32.5%) as of 2024. The proportion of cases with acute disease onset remained practically unchanged between 1984 and 2024, with the differences not being statistically significant [RR-0.97; 95% CI - 0.825-1.15; χ^2 -0.11; p>0.05].

Table 1

40-year changes in the characteristics of schizophrenia onset with various courses in the adult population of the valley

No	Forms of schizophrenia onset	Epidemiological monitoring years, frequency of detection of schizophrenia				OR	95% CI	χ^2	p
		1984		2024					
		n	%	n	%				
1	Acute onset	146	33.4	211	32.5	0.97	0.825-1.15	0.11	> 0.05
2	Onset with primary disorders	291	66.6	439	67.5	1.17	1.08-1.27	15.61	<0.001
3	<i>Onset with asthenic-neurosis-like disorders</i>	82	18.8	118	18.2	0.97	0.75-1.25	0.065	> 0.05
	<i>Onset with negative disorders</i>	56	12.8	100	15.4	1.20	0.89-1.63	1.40	> 0.05
	<i>Onset with psychopathic-like disorders</i>	39	8.9	74	11.4	1.28	0.88-1.84	1.70	> 0.05

<i>Onset with thymopathic disorders</i>	39	8.9	75	11.5	1.29	0.90-1.87	1.90	> 0.05
<i>Onset with reduction of psychoenergetic potential</i>	75	17.2	72	11.1	0.65	0.48-0.87	8.28	< 0.05

The number of patients with a gradual onset of the disease with primary disorders totaled 730 (67.2%), of which 291 (66.6%) were as of 1984 and 439 (67.5%) as of 2024. The change in the frequency of gradual disease onset between 1984 and 2024 was statistically significant [RR-1.17; 95% CI - 1.08-1.27; χ^2 -15.61, $p < 0.001$]. The fact that the gradual onset of schizophrenia is currently more common indicates a change in the dynamics of schizophrenia.

The total number of patients with asthenic-neurosis-like disorders was 200 (32.8%), of which 82 (18.8%) were as of 1984 and 118 (18.2%) as of 2024. The proportion of cases with initial asthenic-neurosis-like disorders at the onset of the disease in the period 1984-2024 remained practically

unchanged, and the differences are statistically insignificant [RR-0.97; 95% CI - 0.75-1.25; χ^2 -0.065; $p > 0.05$].

The number of patients whose disease began with negative symptoms was 156 (14.4%), of which 56 (12.8%) were reported in 1984 and 100 (15.4%) in 2024. In 2024, the number of cases with negative symptoms at the initial stage of the disease increased, but this increase is not statistically significant [OR-1.20; 95% CI - 0.89-1.63; χ^2 -1.40; $p > 0.05$].

The number of patients whose illness began with psychopathic-like disorders totaled 113 (10.4%), of which 39 (8.9%) were reported in 1984 and 74 (11.4%) in 2024. The proportion of cases with psychopathic-like initial disorders at the onset of the disease increased in 2024; however, these differences are not statistically significant [OR-1.28; 95% CI - 0.88-1.84; χ^2 -1.70; $p > 0.05$].

The number of patients whose disease began with thymopathic disorders was 114 (10.5%), of which 39 (8.9%) were reported in 1984 and 75 (11.5%) in 2024. In 2024, the proportion of cases associated with primary thymopathic disorders at the onset of the disease increased; however, these differences are not statistically significant [OR-1.29; 95% CI - 0.90-1.87; χ^2 -1.90; $p > 0.05$].

The number of patients with disease onset characterized by reduced energy potential totaled only 147 (13.5%), of which 75 (17.2%) were as of 1984 and 72 (11.1%) as of 2024. The proportion of initial disorders related to decreased energy potential significantly declined in 2024 compared to 1984, and this reduction is statistically significant [OR-0.65; 95% CI - 0.48-0.87; χ^2 -8.28; $p < 0.05$].

Compared to 1984, the proportion of acute disease onset cases decreased in 2024. This decline is statistically significant and may indicate a change in the clinical presentation of the disease, namely that the acute form of disease onset is becoming less common.

Overall, the following results warrant particular attention. The proportion of cases where the disease began with negative disorders increased, and this change is statistically significant. This may reflect an intensification of negative symptoms in the initial stages of the disease.

The proportion of cases beginning with asthenic-neurosis-like disorders remains high; however, a slight decrease was observed between 1984 and 2024. The differences are statistically insignificant, indicating a stable position of these disorders in the structure of disease onset.

The proportion of psychopathic-like disorders at disease onset remained virtually unchanged, with statistically insignificant differences. This indicates stability in the manifestation of this type of disorder.

The frequency of thymopathic disorders at the onset of the disease remained unchanged from 1984 to 2024. The differences are statistically insignificant, indicating the stability of their role.

The proportion of cases where the disease began with reduced energy potential decreased significantly in 2024, and this change is statistically significant. This may indicate a decrease in emotional deficit in the initial stages of the disease.

General trends manifest as follows. A significant decrease was observed in the proportion of cases with acute onset and onset with reduced energy potential, which indicates a change in the clinical presentation patterns of the disease. At the same time, the proportion of negative symptoms increased, indicating a rise in their significance in the structure of disease onset.

The analysis results indicate changes in the characteristics of disease onset during the study period. The decrease in the proportion of acute onset cases and the increase in cases beginning with negative symptoms may be related to improvements in diagnostic methods, changes in external factors, or alterations in the biological mechanisms of the disease.

Table 2

General comparative characteristics of disease onset in patients for 1984 and 2024

No	Years of study	Acute onset	Started with primary disorders	OR	95% CI	χ^2	p
1	1984	146 (33.4%)	291 (66.6%)	0.50	0.43- 0.58	94.90	<0.001
2	2024	211 (32.5%)	439 (67.5%)	0.60	0.51- 0.71	38.91	<0.001

A comparative analysis of the number and proportion of patients with acute and gradual onset of the disease with primary disorders was conducted for the years 1984 and 2024. The analysis included calculations of relative risk (RR), 95% confidence interval (CI), chi-square test results, and p-values.

1984 Results: Acute onset of the disease: 146 (33.4%). Gradual onset of the disease with initial symptoms: 291 (66.6%) [RR - 0.50, 95% CI - 0.43 - 0.58, χ^2 - 94.90, p < 0.001]. This is a highly significant result, indicating that the gradual onset of the disease was statistically significantly more common than the acute onset.

2024 Results: Acute onset of the disease: 211 (32.5%). Gradual onset of the disease with primary symptoms: 439 (67.5%) [RR - 0.60, 95% CI - 0.51-0.71, χ^2 - 38.91, p<0.001]. This is also a significant result, indicating that the gradual onset of the disease was statistically significantly more common in 2024 compared to the acute onset.

Conclusion

The overall conclusion from the results is that between 1984 and 2024, the gradual onset of schizophrenia consistently prevailed over the acute onset. Moreover, while acute onset was 50% less common in 1984, this difference decreased to 40% in 2024. This trend is statistically significant, as the p-value for both cases is <0.001 . The likelihood of acute onset of the disease in 2024 has relatively increased compared to 1984, that is, 40 years later, and this change is still considered statistically significant.

REFERENCES

1. Bleuler E. Schizophrenia. Split Brain and Split Consciousness. - Moscow: Mir, 2000.
2. Clinical Psychiatry / Edited by N. G. Neznanov. - St. Petersburg: Piter, 2017.
3. Tyulpin Yu. G., Mazo G. E. Epidemiology of Schizophrenia: Retrospective and Prospective Aspects. - S.S. Korsakov Journal of Neurology and Psychiatry, 2021. - No. 9.
4. Fedorov A.A., Belyaeva N.V. Preventive strategies in the treatment of schizophrenia. // Journal of Clinical Psychiatry. - 2023. - 25 (2), p. 66-73.
5. Cotton S., Lambert M., Schimmelmann B., Mackinnon et al. Differences between first episode schizophrenia and schizoaffective disorder. // Schizophrenia Research. - 2013. 147 (1), 169-174.
6. World Health Organization. Schizophrenia. WHO Fact Sheet. 2022. [<https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/schizophrenia>].
7. McGrath J., Saha S., Chant D., Welham J. Schizophrenia: a concise overview of incidence, prevalence, and mortality. - Epidemiol Rev. 2008;30:67-76.
8. Owen M.J., Sawa A., Mortensen P.B. Schizophrenia. - Lancet. 2016;388 (10039):86-97.